

OLONITE RULE OF JUDGMENTAL BASIS

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The Olonite Rule of Judgmental Basis (ORJB) asserts that for any sample to be valid, the size must be equal to or above the half of the total population in consideration. The rule follows and supports the Olonite Sampling Technique, Olonite Proportional Allocation Method, and the Olonite Two-Third-Point-Five Rule (Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (O2/3.5R) which affirms that the strength of the results gotten from a questionnaire or survey analysis is being determined by the size of the sample i.e. the closer the sample size to the total population, the more reliance and closer to reality the results are and the far a sample size is to the half of the total population, the far the result will be to reality. A sample size should be half of the total population or far above the half. Exactly half is good, a bit above the half is better while far above half is best. These Technique, Method and Rule are discussed below:

The Olonite Sampling Technique is a sampling method that is used for small and large population. It was developed as a solution to the short comings of the Taro Yamane Sampling Technique. OST ranges from “1 – 1,280,000,000 (one - one billion two hundred and eighty million) population” and 1 - 59,500, having two (2) categories with 7 and 3 versions respectively. OST asserts that for some set of levels of significance, a particular category and version of sampling formulae should be adopted; level of significance 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.2, 0.01, 0.002 and 0.001 should focus on the category 1 and use the total population to know the version to be considered. For level of significance 0.4, 0.3, and 0.2, the category 2 should be considered and the total population should be used to determine the version to be considered. The Olonite Sampling Technique supports the 2/3 rule to a logical extent. Taro Yamane Sampling Method can only be used for populations below “four hundred (400)” and using Taro Yamane for a population above 400 might not give us a result closer to reality as the half value will not be attained using the Taro Yamane Sampling Technique but the Olonite Sampling Technique (Olonite, 2021).

Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) is a method used to allocate sample to strata based on the strata variances and similar sampling in the strata. An Olonite Allocation scheme provides the most precision for estimating a population mean given a fixed or flexible branch/departmental/group total sample. It can be used to select allocations/samples from Organizations, Countries, States, etc that have scattered branches, states, cities, etc. It was developed as a solution to the short comings of the Taro Yamane and Bourley’s Proportional

Allocation Technique. The OPAM advocates for the use of any of the two procedures in achieving an optimal sample size and distribution size using the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) to sample from each stratum of a strata or the OPAM formulae. In this case, the strata can be seen an Organization, State, Country, etc while the stratum represents departments, Cities, States respectively, etc. OPAM asserts that the higher the population, the higher the sample and distribution size should be per branch, departments, groups, etc, this will give an optimum representation for each stratum to be considered and selected. The Olonite Proportional Allocation Method helps to reduce time wastage while trying to appropriate a perfect set/population i.e. Organizations having the same no of departments and staff or Organizations having the different no of departments and staff. Olonite Allocation is always the best proportional allocation method (since Olonite Allocation is optimal) (Olonite, 2021).

Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (O2/3.5R) is a selection rule employed to reduce the stress of researchers who are to sample a large population while maintaining the optimal selection from the large population. Using a three sampling/selection techniques, the result showed that the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule gives a more flexible result for researchers as seen in table 1. The rule provides the most precision for estimating a population as it supports the 1/2 and 2/3 rule. Olonite Rule is always the best rule when a population is large and a researcher must sample the required size taking into consideration, the optimum sampling size which should be half of the total population and a little bit above. The rule states: “the closer a sample size to its total population, the more reliance the result”. The rule is recommended to be used all over institutions and world. It is time to appreciate the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule in Academics and for sampling purposes (Olonite, 2021).

References

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